

Co-folding of Carbohydrate-Protein Complexes

Francesca Peccati^{*,†,‡}

[†]*Center for Cooperative Research in Biosciences (CIC bioGUNE), Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA) Bizkaia Technology Park, 48160 Derio, Spain*

[‡]*Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, 48013 Bilbao, Spain*

E-mail: fpeccati@cicbiogune.es

Phone: +34 946 572 538

Abstract

Deep learning-based methods have transformed *in silico* protein structure prediction, and co-folding approaches now enable the generation of three-dimensional protein models from sequence in the presence of cofactors and custom ligands, unlocking major opportunities in drug discovery and design. Nonetheless, co-folded models remain limited by factors such as a difficult-to-quantify reliance on pose memorization from training data, and violations of geometric and stereochemical constraints. In this context, protein-carbohydrate interactions are particularly challenging to model accurately owing to the high density of chiral centers of the ligands, the flexibility of glycosidic linkages, and the typically exposed nature of binding sites. In this contribution, we assess the performance of two widely used deep learning models, AlphaFold3 and Boltz-2, in predicting carbohydrate-protein complex structures. Using three carbohydrate-binding protein families, we show that accurate geometries of bound states and insights into protein-carbohydrate recognition specificity can be obtained directly from co-folded models generated using only protein sequence and a simple ligand string notation, paving the way for the high-throughput screening of glycans and glycomimetics.

Introduction

The latest generation of artificial intelligence models for protein structure prediction enables the generation of full-atom macromolecular models with unprecedented accuracy, simultaneously predicting the geometries of noncovalently interacting species—including nucleic acids, proteins, ligands, and ions—as well as covalently bound post-translational modifications.¹⁻³ Co-folding, which consists of predicting a protein structure in the presence of a ligand from protein sequence information alone, is an attractive concept in the context of drug development, as opposed to classical molecular docking.⁴ Docking approaches require a high-quality three-dimensional structure of the receptor, often prior knowledge of the putative binding site, and typically involve only partial conformational sampling of the receptor. Therefore, they are subject to limitations when the target protein structure is unavailable, of low quality, or only available in the *holo* form with a different ligand, as induced fit can modify the receptor conformation.⁵⁻⁷ The ability to predict protein–ligand complex structures directly from sequence overcomes these limitations, as the binding pose emerges naturally from the simultaneous generation of the coordinates of the binding partners.⁴

While it remains under debate to what extent co-folding is generalizable across all ligand classes, ligands and poses most frequently encountered during training are predicted with higher accuracy than rarely seen ones, owing to memorization effects;^{8,9} therefore, extensive benchmarking is required to explore its limitations, particularly in the context of specific interactions that are challenging to predict using classical methods. Among the several available models for co-folding, AlphaFold3 (AF3) currently sets the accuracy benchmark, especially for difficult tasks such as antibody–antigen structure prediction.¹ Another recently released model is Boltz-2 (Bo2), which enables both structure and affinity prediction, and offers a high degree of controllability through conditioning and steering.³ These include the choice of prediction method (generating ensembles that resemble X-ray crystallography, NMR, or molecular dynamics), the ability to enforce structural templates, and the specification of distance and pocket constraints. Additionally, it allows the application

of physics-based potentials during inference to reduce unphysical predictions.³ Both models share common drawbacks typical of deep learning-based co-folding approaches, such as steric clashes, incorrect assignment of chiral centers, and distorted bond lengths and angles,³ which can be particularly problematic in the prediction of co-folded carbohydrate-protein complexes.

Carbohydrate-protein interactions are highly relevant to a range of biological phenomena, including infection and immunity^{10,11} and tumor growth and metastasis.¹² Lectins are non-enzymatic carbohydrate-binding proteins that decode glycan information on cell surfaces and regulate recognition,¹³ adhesion,¹⁴ and signaling.¹⁵ They exert their functions by engaging specific glycan motifs through multivalent, often low-affinity contacts that achieve high avidity at the cell interface.^{13,16} Because lectin-glycan recognition underlies disease processes in infection, inflammation, and cancer, small-molecule glycomimetics are attractive candidates to inhibit or allosterically modulate lectin function for therapeutic purposes and targeted delivery.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ Therefore, studying the interactions of lectins with glycans and glycomimetics is of significant biological and therapeutic relevance.

As glycan-lectin affinities are generally weak (in the low millimolar range), biological recognition exploits multivalency, generating large, heterogeneous complexes. This makes the study of their interactions particularly challenging and necessitates the combination of multiple techniques, spanning from X-ray crystallography,²⁰ to NMR,²¹ to isothermal titration calorimetry.²² Notably, NMR enables the quantification of weak, multivalent glycan-lectin interactions in solution while simultaneously providing information on affinity, kinetics, epitope mapping, conformation, and dynamics through complementary ligand- and receptor-observed experiments.²¹

The low affinity of glycan-lectin interactions is encoded in their structure. Carbohydrates are relatively ordered, hydroxyl-dense ligands that mimic structured water, binding lectins through a combination of hydrogen bonds and interactions with aromatic amino acids.^{23,24} Carbohydrates exhibit extreme structural diversity, with a high density of stereocenters, high

conformational flexibility, variable linkage positions, branching, and extensive post-synthetic modifications.²⁵ Lectins bind specific glycans with high precision via structurally tailored, and typically shallow, carbohydrate-binding sites, where the displacement of structured water molecules is an important entropic drive for binding.^{24,26,27}

All these characteristics make glycan–lectin interactions extremely challenging to predict using traditional computational techniques, thereby limiting the potential impact of computer modeling on their engineering and characterization. In this context, co-folding has the potential to advance the computational study of carbohydrate–protein interactions—provided it can yield accurate binding poses and recapitulate the exquisite selectivity of these recognition processes, particularly with respect to the complex stereochemistry and conformational diversity of glycans.

A recent study addresses the use of AF3 to predict the structures of complex glycans, highlighting important limitations in the conformational diversity (flexibility) achievable in glycoprotein prediction, and suggesting a bias originating from the PDB training subset.²⁸ In this work, we build on that knowledge by evaluating the ability of AF3 and Bo2 to predict co-folded carbohydrate–protein complex structures through the collective analysis of multiple co-folding solutions, i.e., *ensembles* of conformations. We demonstrate that such collective analysis can provide valuable insights into binding propensity and selectivity. By examining three families of carbohydrate-binding proteins, we highlight the strengths and limitations of co-folding. We show not only that these models can generate accurate complex geometries, but also that co-folding represents a powerful approach to explore the specificity of carbohydrate–protein recognition using only protein sequence information and a one-dimensional, text-based notation for ligand representation—thus opening the door to high-throughput screening of protein–carbohydrate interactions.

Figure 1: Carbohydrate–protein pairs analyzed in this study. CRD: carbohydrate recognition domain. SLBR: Siglec-like binding region. Crystallographic structures of the modeled proteins are shown, highlighting the binding unit or motif and the key amino acids involved in the interaction. Human galectin-3 CRD: PDB ID 3ZSJ;²⁹ human DC-SIGN CRD: PDB ID 1SL5;³⁰ SLBR Siglec subdomain from *S. gordonii* strain M99, named GspB: PDB ID 5IUC;³¹ SLBR Siglec subdomain from *S. gordonii* strain Challis, named Hsa: PDB ID 6X3Q.³²

The systems under study are shown in Figure 1 and include the carbohydrate recognition domain (CRD) of a representative galectin (human galectin-3, henceforth Gal3), that of a representative C-type lectin (human DC-SIGN), and two sialic acid-binding immunoglobulin-type lectins (siglec) subdomains of streptococcal siglec-like binding regions (henceforth SLBRs). Gal3, which specifically recognizes galactose, is used in this work to gauge co-folding models’ stereochemical fidelity when presented with disaccharide ligands containing the galactose unit, its C4 epimer glucose, and fluorinated glucose analogs. DC-SIGN, which binds glycans through Ca^{2+} -mediated interactions, is used to investigate whether co-folding can generate higher-order (protein–ion–carbohydrate) binding poses that satisfy the optimal binding epitope³³ in both monosaccharides and a tetrasaccharide histo blood group antigen.³⁴ Finally, SLBR domains from two different streptococcal strains are used to evaluate co-folding models’ ability to predict highly challenging interactions, specifically those involving diverse and

flexible hypervariable loops within domains homologous to the large and varied immunoglobulin superfamily, which critically influence recognition of a panel of sialylated glycans.³²

Methods

Ligands preparation

Three-dimensional models for all mono- and oligosaccharides were prepared using the Glycam Carbohydrate Builder³⁵ (<https://glycam.org/cb/>) and downloaded in PDB format. The structures were then converted to chiral SMILES format using Open Babel³⁶ version 2.3.1, with the standard `-osmiles` flag. Although SMILES is not the only acceptable input format for co-folding models, it was selected for its simplicity—requiring no specialized glycobiology expertise—and with the aim of enabling large-scale ligand screening. In contrast, structural formats such as CCD files require manual curation of monosaccharide fragments, making them less amenable to high-throughput workflows.²⁸ All ligand structures in SMILES format are available as supplementary materials. Interestingly, despite the fact that ring conformation information is not present in the SMILES format—which encodes only atomic connectivity—the vast majority of co-folded models correctly predict the most stable ring conformation for each monosaccharide (4C_1 for Glc, Gal, Man, GlcNAc, and GalNAc; 1C_4 for Fuc; and 2C_5 for Neu5Ac). The only exception is a minority of structures of the histo blood group antigen A type VI, in which the Fuc ring adopts an inverted chair conformation (4C_1). Full conformational assignments of all co-folded models are available as supplementary materials.

AF3 structure prediction

AF3 structure predictions were performed using codebase version 3.0.1 with default settings, generating 100 seeds, with 5 diffusion samples per seed (500 models in total). *json* data files for all predictions are available as supplementary materials.

Bo2 structure prediction

Bo2 structure predictions were performed using version 2.2.0, employing the “x-ray diffraction” method with 10 recycling steps and 200 sampling steps. One hundred predictions were generated, with 5 diffusion samples each (500 models in total). No contact or pocket conditioning was applied, so that co-folding was performed without steering the interaction toward any specific region. The `--usepotentials` flag was activated to apply a guiding potential during the diffusion process, improving the quality of ligand geometries. Input files in *yaml* format for all predictions are available as supplementary materials. The Multiple Sequence Alignment (MSA) server (<https://api.colabfold.com>) was used for generating the MSAs.

Analysis

Geometry analysis of the predicted models—including the assignment of the absolute configuration of stereocenters and ring conformations, ligand RMSD calculations with respect to crystallographic structures, and classification of binding modes—was performed using Python3 scripts provided in the ESI. The configuration of the anomeric carbon was not considered when evaluating stereochemical fidelity. Confidence analysis was carried out by examining the interface predicted template modelling (ipTM) scores of the structure ensembles generated with AF3 and Bo2. Of note, neither model includes an explicit penalty term for violations of the absolute configuration of chiral centers; therefore, ipTM scores should be interpreted as a measure of the confidence in the overall co-folded complex structure, independently of the accuracy of the ligand stereochemistry.

Results and discussion

Stereochemistry of Gal3 recognition of glycans and glycomimetics

The S-face canonical CRD of Gal3 recognizes galactose through a combination of CH- π interactions with W181 and multiple hydrogen bonds. High selectivity toward galactose arises from a pair of hydrogen bonds involving His158 and Arg162, which engage the axial hydroxyl group at position 4 (O4). For each co-folding model and ligand, we generated an ensemble of 500 structures and analyzed them collectively by assigning the absolute configuration of each chiral center and evaluating structural similarity to available experimental references.²⁹ Both AF3 and Bo2 predict the binding of lactose and N-acetyllactosamine (LacNAc) to Gal3 with high confidence and low geometric dispersion across the co-folded ensembles. All predicted structures display the correct disaccharide stereochemistry and show strong agreement with high-resolution crystallographic reference structures of the complexes (RMSD < 1 Å; Figures 2A, 2B, and S1).^{29,37} While Bo2 yields a more structurally diverse ensemble—particularly in the flexible N-terminal region—the predicted binding pose is highly accurate, with a unique conformation of the key interacting residues that closely resembles the crystallographic structure of the complex (Figure 2C).

Based on this positive result, we challenged the co-folding models with cellobiose, a disaccharide that differs from lactose exclusively in the configuration of a C4 atom, in which the binding galactose unit is replaced by glucose. Interestingly, neither AF3 nor Bo2 predicts cellobiose with the correct stereochemistry in any of the 500 predicted structures (0% correct chirality, Figure 2A). Instead, both models epimerize the C4 carbon of the non-reducing end Glc unit, yielding structurally indistinguishable predictions from those generated for lactose. This result is significant because it clearly demonstrates that stereochemical violations in these ligands are not random, but are instead induced by the context of the receptor. In other words, the models have learned that galectins bind lactose analogues, and consequently impose a stereochemical distortion that converts glucose into the preferred galactose epimer,

favoring binding over stereochemical fidelity during co-folding. As a result, the analysis of stereochemical violations in co-folded structures may carry valuable information about the binding preferences of CRDs. Of note, a symmetric galactose to glucose stereochemical violation was recently reported in a study benchmarking AF3’s ability to predict the structures of large glycans.²⁸

Figure 2: A) Percentage of models predicted with the correct ligand stereochemistry using AF3 and Bo2. B) Overlay of 500 co-folded structures of lactose bound to Gal3, predicted by AF3 and Bo2. C) Crystallographic structure of lactose bound to Gal3.²⁹ D) Overlay of 77 AF3-predicted co-folded models of 4-*deoxy*-4-fluorocellobiose (left) and of 30 AF3-predicted co-folded models of 2,3,4-*deoxy*-2,3,4-trifluorocellobiose (right). E) Representative Bo2-predicted co-folded models of 4-*deoxy*-4-fluorocellobiose (left) and 2,3,4-*deoxy*-2,3,4-trifluorocellobiose (right). Key residues involved in ligand binding are shown as pale cyan sticks. Fluorine atoms are represented as orange spheres. Glc, fluorinated Glc and Gal are shown as blue, pink and yellow sticks, respectively.

Motivated by these findings, we sought to further investigate this phenomenon and assess the extent to which stereochemical violations affect the co-folding of ligands that are not strictly natural carbohydrates. As straightforward models of glycomimetics, we examined two analogs: 4-*deoxy*-4-fluorocellobiose and 2,3,4-*deoxy*-2,3,4-trifluorocellobiose. With these ligands, we observed divergent behavior between the two co-folding models: while Bo2

continues to fail in predicting the correct stereochemistry across all generated structures, AF3 recovers a small subset of complexes with the correct chirality (6–15%, Figure 2A). Analysis of the correctly folded 4-*deoxy*-4-fluorocellobiose complexes reveals a binding pose similar to that predicted for lactose, which is incompatible with Arg162 binding, possibly reflecting a memorized lactose-bound conformation (Figure 2D, left). With 2,3,4-*deoxy*-2,3,4-trifluorocellobiose—AF3 predicts a small fraction of structures with the correct stereochemistry, but with higher structural diversity (Figure 2D, right) and lower prediction confidence (Figure S2). These results indicate that AF3 is highly responsive to changes in ligand composition. Conversely, analysis of Bo2 predictions reveals that this model systematically misassigns the configuration of the critical C4 stereocenter irrespective of the chemical identity of the disaccharide, consistently yielding a lactose-like binding pose with only a marginal decrease in prediction confidence (Figure S2). Overall, Bo2 exhibits lower sensitivity to variations in ligand composition. Notably, Bo2 predictions were not steered toward any specific binding pocket, allowing the model to explore not only the canonical carbohydrate-binding site on the S-face, but also potential noncanonical binding modes on the F-face.³⁸

Prediction and ranking of alternative structural binding patterns in DC-SIGN

DC-SIGN recognizes monosaccharides through a conserved Ca^{2+} -chelating vicinal diol “minimum binding epitope” with fixed axial chirality, which can be classified into three sugar-agnostic structural binding patterns.³³ Classification of these patterns requires the definition of a reference plane, illustrated in Figure 3A. This plane is defined by the three Ca^{2+} ions and bisects the CO–CO vector of the minimum binding epitope, assigning the solvent-exposed oxygen as ^+O and the opposing oxygen—located proximally to Glu354—as ^-O .³³

The different binding modes of monosaccharides containing the minimal binding epitope can be classified as follows: **A**, in which both coordinating oxygens are equatorial

($^+O_{eq}/^-O_{eq}$); **B1**, in which ^+O is axial and ^-O is equatorial ($^+O_{ax}/^-O_{eq}$); and **B2**, in which ^+O is equatorial and ^-O is axial ($^+O_{eq}/^-O_{ax}$).³³ Enumerating the CO–CO pairs in D-mannose and L-fucose with respect to the position of the binding hydroxyl groups yields binding poses 2–3, 3–2, 3–4, and 4–3, which correspond to these structural binding patterns.³³ A combination of NMR and molecular dynamics data has recently shown that **B1** is the dominant and most stable binding mode, as it preserves the Ca^{2+} chelation, introduces a hydrogen bond between an adjacent equatorial hydroxyl and Glu354 (O2 in L-fucose and O4 in D-Man), and forms hydrophobic contacts with Val351 (Figure 3A).³³

Figure 3: A) Graphical depiction of the reference plane (vertical line), bisecting the minimal binding epitope of carbohydrates binding to DC-SIGN (in black) into two regions, arbitrarily defined as $^+$ and $^-$. Adapted from Ref. 33. B) Percentage of models predicted with the correct ligand stereochemistry using AF3 and Bo2. C) Binding modes of α -OMe-L-fucose (FucOME) to DC-SIGN predicted by AF3. For binding mode **B1**, the AF3-predicted structure (white cartoon) is overlaid with the crystallographic structure (pink cartoon) of DC-SIGN complexed with the L-fucose LNFP III tetrasaccharide, shown as lines (PDB ID 1SL5).³⁰ D) Binding modes of α -OMe-D-mannose (ManOME) to DC-SIGN predicted by AF3. Residues Glu354 and Val351 are shown as pale cyan sticks. Residues coordinating the primary Ca^{2+} ions are depicted as lines. Ca^{2+} ions are shown as green spheres; those from the reference PDB structure 1SL5 are shown as orange spheres. Oxygen atoms involved in Ca^{2+} coordination or forming secondary interactions with Val351 and Glu354 are labeled. Fuc, Man, GlcNAc and Gal are shown as red, green, blue and yellow sticks, respectively.

These characteristics make DC-SIGN an optimal benchmark system for evaluating co-folding models’ ability to predict and discriminate between alternative binding poses. Interactions with α -OMe-L-fucose (FucOMe) and α -OMe-D-mannose (ManOMe) were co-folded as assemblies comprising one DC-SIGN unit, three Ca^{2+} ions (corresponding to the primary carbohydrate-binding site and two auxiliary calcium sites³⁹), and one monosaccharide unit. Analysis of the stereochemistry of the resulting co-folded structures shows that both AF3 and Bo2 predict a majority of correct stereoisomers for FucOMe, whereas Bo2’s performance drops for ManOMe, with fewer than one fourth of the structures displaying the correct ligand chirality (Figure 3B). The positions of all three Ca^{2+} ions are consistently predicted correctly at the primary and auxiliary binding sites with both models.³⁹

Stereochemically correct structures were then classified into the **A**, **B1**, and **B2** binding modes (see ESI for the classification criteria), as summarized in Table 1. AF3 produces greater structural diversity than Bo2, predicting three out of four binding poses for FucOMe and all four possible binding poses for ManOMe (Figures S3 and S4). Representative AF3-predicted structures are shown in Figure 3C. The majority of Bo2-predicted models for FucOMe could not be classified due to excessively long oxygen–calcium coordination distances. Interestingly, the dominant **B1** 4–3 pose is also the most frequently predicted by AF3 and displays high structural similarity to a crystallographic structure of a bound fucose residue within the LNFP III tetrasaccharide ligand.³⁰ In the **B1** pose, the equatorial O2 oxygen consistently lies within hydrogen bonding distance of Glu354 ($< 3 \text{ \AA}$, Figure S5) in all models, in agreement with the proposed stabilizing role of this interaction.³³ The **B1** 2–3 pose is likewise the most frequent one among AF3 co-folded structures with ManOMe (Figure 3D), with the O4 oxygen lying within 3 \AA of Glu354 in most models (Figures S6 and S7). Similarly, in the **B1** poses of both FucOMe and ManOMe, Val351 lies approximately 4 \AA from the carbohydrate (Figures S5–S7), consistent with its contribution to binding via weak non-polar interactions.

Overall, these results demonstrate that co-folding with AF3 is a powerful approach that

enables, in a rapid and automated manner, not only the screening of alternative candidate binding poses, but also the estimation of their relative likelihood based on ensemble frequency. Of note, previous work has shown that the relative populations of alternative conformations in AlphaFold-predicted ensembles correlate with experimentally observed conformational distributions in an alternate-frame folding system,⁴⁰ supporting the view that structure ensembles generated by (co-)folding models can serve as informative proxies for the underlying conformational populations.

Table 1: Number of structures out of 500 predictions generated with AF3 and Bo2 for DC-SIGN co-folded with α -OMe-L-fucose (FucOMe) and α -OMe-D-mannose (ManOMe), classified into structural binding patterns **A**, **B1**, and **B2**. Classification required both coordinating oxygens (2-3, 3-2, 3-4, or 4-3) to be within 2.7 Å of the primary Ca²⁺ ion. Models that could not be assigned to any defined binding mode are categorized as “other”.

Ligand	structural binding pattern	n. AF3 models	n. Bo2 models
FucOMe	B1 4-3	298	3
FucOMe	B2 3-4	0	0
FucOMe	A 2-3	1	44
FucOMe	A 3-2	62	0
FucOMe	other	23	386
ManOMe	B1 2-3	235	0
ManOMe	B2 3-2	36	0
ManOMe	A 3-4	8	0
ManOMe	A 4-3	129	95
ManOMe	other	44	11

Finally, we tested the co-folding models by predicting DC-SIGN complexes with a more complex tetrasaccharide—specifically, the histo blood group antigen A type VI—known to bind DC-SIGN primarily through fucose, with additional secondary interactions involving a GalNAc unit.³⁴ This ligand contains 19 chiral centers (excluding the anomeric carbon at reducing end, see Methods), and since only two of the four constituent monosaccharides engage directly with the receptor, it represents an extremely challenging test case in the context of stereochemistry violations. Indeed, only AF3 predicts a small fraction of structures (4%) with the correct stereochemistry albeit with low confidence (Figures 3B and S8), and in these cases the ligand binds incorrectly via glucose or galactose—which do not possess the

minimal binding epitope—instead of the correct fucose residue (Figure S9).

These results indicate that, while co-folding is highly effective in predicting binding modes for individual monosaccharides, its accuracy degrades with increasing ligand size and stereochemical complexity, especially when binding to the receptor involves only a fraction of the saccharide units of the system. A recent study on glycoprotein prediction with AF3 shows that stereochemical plausibility can depend on the format used for providing ligand information, and specifically that structural formats can improve prediction over the text format (SMILES) used in this work.²⁸ However, the use of structure formats requires curated monosaccharide libraries capable of correctly handling glycosidic linkages and leaving atoms, which limits standardization and ease-of-use.

Selectivity of ligand recognition in siglec-like binding regions

Siglec-like binding regions (SLBRs), adhesive modules found within streptococcal serine-rich repeat proteins, mediate binding to sialic acid-containing glycans on host glycoproteins. The specific glycans recognized by these regions play a key role in determining whether a bacterial strain behaves as a harmless commensal or adopts an invasive, pathogenic phenotype. For example, SLBRs that preferentially bind the sialyl-T antigen are associated with increased virulence in endocarditis models, underscoring the central role of glycan selectivity in modulating host–pathogen interactions.³²

At the structural level, selectivity is governed by three hypervariable loops that flank the conserved sialic acid-binding motif within the Ig-like fold of SLBRs: the CD, EF, and FG loops (Figure 4B). These loops introduce variability into the binding pocket, enabling discrimination among closely related glycans that share the common Neu5Ac α 2,3Gal unit. The EF loop confers flexibility that supports broad specificity; the FG loop imposes steric constraints that exclude fucosylated or extensively elaborated glycans; and the CD loop modulates electrostatic compatibility with sulfated ligands (Figure 4B, see Figure S10 for more details).³² Chimeragenesis and mutational analyses have shown that even single-loop

modifications can alter glycan-binding specificity, demonstrating that structural plasticity in these loops underlies bacterial adaptation to host glycomes.³²

From a modeling perspective, the involvement of hypervariable loops—regions that are both flexible and structurally diverse—introduces a significant challenge, as identifying the correct binding pose requires extensive conformational sampling of these elements. Therefore, the ability to directly co-fold ligands with siglec and siglec-like domains would represent a major opportunity for the *in silico* prediction of binding affinity and glycan selectivity. To illustrate this, we used co-folding to evaluate the selectivity of the SLBR siglec domains from two different strains of *S. gordonii*. Strain M99 (henceforth GspB) exhibits narrow selectivity, preferentially binding the sialyl-T (sT) and not binding the 3'sialyl-LacNAc (3'sLn) ligand. By contrast, strain Challis (henceforth Hsa) displays broader selectivity, binding a range of sialoglycans, including 3'sLn.³²

For each strain, we co-folded the SLBR siglec domain with both sT and 3'sLn ligands. Interestingly, AF3 and Bo2 show markedly different performance in predicting the correct chirality of co-folded structures for the highly selective GspB: while the majority of AF3-predicted models display correct ligand chirality, only a minority of Bo2 predictions do so (Figure 4A). For the more broadly selective Hsa, both models successfully recapitulate the correct ligand chirality.

Figure 4: A) Percentage of models predicted with the correct ligand stereochemistry using AF3 and Bo2. B) Overlay of AF3-predicted co-folded structures of the GspB-sT (left) and GspB-3'sLn (right) complexes. The three hypervariable loops encoding selectivity—CD, EF, and FG—are shown in green, blue, and light brown, respectively. C) Histograms of prediction confidence scores (ipTM) for ensembles of 500 co-folded structures for the GspB-sT, GspB-3'sLn, Hsa-sT, and Hsa-3'sLn complexes. Bars in green indicate models with correct ligand stereochemistry; red bars indicate models with stereochemical violations.

Figure 4B shows an overlay of the structures co-folded with AF3. These display negligible geometric dispersion, with the sT ligand predicted at high precision relative to the reference crystallographic structure (Figure S11, RMSD < 1 Å), and accompanied by high confidence scores (ipTM, Figure 4C), indicating that AF3 accurately captures the structural features of this interaction. In contrast, when presented with 3'sLn—a ligand not recognized by GspB—AF3 predicts a broad ensemble of geometries characterized by variable orientations of the GlcNAc unit, which fails to engage the FG and CD loops, while maintaining correct positioning of the Neu5Ac α 2,3Gal disaccharide. This is associated with a decrease in ipTM scores (Figure 4C) and an increased frequency of stereochemical violations. These results are consistent with the observations made for Gal3, reinforcing the notion that increased

structural variability across co-folded ensembles, together with reduced predicted confidence, correlates with diminished binding specificity.

This conclusion is further supported by co-folding the same ligands with the more broadly selective Hsa domain, for which prediction confidences increase (Figure 4C). In this case, both ligands are predicted with narrow geometric dispersion (Figures 5 and S11) and minimal stereochemical violations (Figure 4A) by both AF3 and Bo2. These results indicate that co-folding—particularly with AF3—not only produces accurate binding poses but also captures ligand selectivity, even in Ig-like β -sandwich folds where binding interfaces are defined by flexible loop regions. This accurate binding pose description implies that co-folding correctly samples loop geometries in a straightforward manner, which is an open challenge for classical methods.^{41,42}

Finally, motivated by these results, we challenged AF3 with a broader panel of ligands to evaluate its response to structural modifications such as fucosylation and O-sulfation, as shown in Figure 5. The experimentally measured affinities of Hsa for these ligands, reported in Ref. 32, follow the trend: sT > sLe^C > 3'sLn > sLe^X > 6S-sLe^X, with sT-like ligands being favored over fucosylated and sulfated variants.

AF3-predicted co-folded ensembles for the same protein–ligand pairs were ranked based on the percentage of models with correct stereochemistry and associated ipTM confidence scores (Figure 5). These predictions show a clear preference for unfucosylated ligands and yield the following predicted affinity trend: sT > 3'sLn > sLe^C > sLe^X > 6S-sLe^X, which closely mirrors the experimental ranking, with the exception of a reversal between 3'sLn and sLe^C, which differ only in a single glycosidic linkage.

This proof-of-concept qualitative *in silico* affinity screening strongly supports the ability of AF3 co-folding to capture subtle, chemically encoded features of glycan-binding selectivity. It highlights co-folding as a robust approach for both ligand screening and probing the structural basis of glycan recognition.

Figure 5: Overlay of AF3 co-folded structures with the correct ligand chirality of the Hsa SLBR siglec domain with a panel of different sialoglycans. The three hypervariable loops encoding selectivity (CD, EF, and FG) are colored in green, blue and light brown, respectively. For each ligand, the percentage of structures with the correct chirality (out of 500 structures) is shown together with the average confidence score (ipTM).

Conclusions

We have demonstrated that co-folding is a powerful tool for characterizing carbohydrate–protein interactions. A critical challenge in glycan co-folding lies in the large number of chiral centers, which represent a major vulnerability for current structure prediction models. Here, we showed that stereochemistry violations in co-folded structures correlate with binding propensity and thus carry meaningful information about interaction quality, as exemplified by Gal3. Our results also underscore the importance of analyzing not just single predictions, but rather ensembles of co-folded complexes. Because co-folding structure prediction is inherently non-deterministic, ensemble analysis provides insight into both the multiplicity of possible binding modes and the population distribution among them—as shown for DC-SIGN. Furthermore, we demonstrated that AF3 accurately reproduces ligand preferences in siglec-like domains as a function of the composition and geometries of hypervariable loops, indicating remarkable predictive power even in the context of conformationally flex-

ible loop-mediated interfaces. Importantly, all predictions were generated using only the protein sequence and a simple text-based representation of the ligand, highlighting the main limitations and the extraordinary potential of *in silico* co-folding for large-scale prediction and mechanistic understanding in glycobiology. Future developments will allow direct quantification of binding affinities, whose accuracy is already in par with more time-consuming classical methods,³ enabling accurate and efficient characterization of protein-carbohydrate interactions.

Data and Software Availability

The following data are available through the Zenodo repository <https://zenodo.org/records/17618082>: AF3 and Bo2 co-folding inputs, AF3 and Bo2 co-folded models and their stereochemistry and ring conformation assignments.

AlphaFold open source code can be downloaded from <https://github.com/google-deepmind/alphafold3>.

PyMOL open source code can be downloaded from <https://github.com/schrodinger/pymol-open-source>. Sample code used for analysis is provided in the ESI.

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Supporting Information Available

Distributions of RMSD values for Gal3 bound to lactose and LacNAc relative to reference crystallographic structures; Bo2-predicted ensembles of Gal3–lactose and Gal3–LacNAc complexes; distributions of prediction confidence scores for Gal3–lactose and Gal3–LacNAc

ensembles predicted with AF3 and Bo2; AF3- and Bo2-predicted ensembles of DC-SIGN in complex with FucOMe and ManOMe; distributions of distances to residues Glu354 and Val351 for FucOMe- and ManOMe-bound DC-SIGN in ensembles predicted with AF3 and Bo2; distributions of prediction confidence scores for DC-SIGN–FucOMe and DC-SIGN–ManOMe ensembles predicted with AF3 and Bo2; AF3-predicted ensemble of the DC-SIGN–blood group antigen A type VI complex; comparison of GspB and Hsa SLBRs; distributions of RMSD values for GspB and Hsa bound to sT and 3’sLn relative to reference crystallographic structures; AF3- and Bo2-predicted ensembles of Hsa in complex with sT and 3’sLn; all protein sequences and ligand text representations of all co-folded binding partners; sample code for assigning the stereochemistry of co-folding solutions, computing RMSD values, assigning ring conformations, classifying DC-SIGN binding poses, and performing confidence-score analyses.

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TOC Graphic

